

SARS IN NEONATOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8050697>

Relevance: SARS is the most common pathology in both children and adults, especially in the winter period of diseases. Inflammation of the mucosa of the upper and lower respiratory tract is accompanied by hypersecretion of viscous mucus, edema of the mucous membrane of the respiratory tract, impaired mucociliary transport and bronchial obstruction. Inflammation of the mucous membrane occurs with the participation of humoral and cellular mediators of inflammation, the main role in this case belongs to the cellular mediator - eicosanoids. Taking into account the peculiarities of the pathogenesis of broncho-obstructive syndrome (BOS), treatment uses mucolytic, expectorant, antihistamine, sedative, bronchodilator and hormonal drugs. However, the treatment does not always provide an anti-inflammatory and drainage effect, and therefore the prevention of bacterial complications, to reduce the pathogenetic mechanisms of the occurrence of broncho-obstructive syndrome, the drug fenspiride (Inspiron) is used. The drug has an anti-inflammatory effect, reduces exudation, swelling of the bronchial mucosa, sputum viscosity, it prevents bronchial obstruction and also helps to reduce and stop the clinical symptom - dry and wet cough. The anti-inflammatory properties of fenspirin have opened up new possibilities for the treatment of acute respiratory diseases and biofeedback in children.

Goal: To evaluate the effectiveness of the drug inspiron in children with acute diseases of the lower respiratory tract accompanied by broncho-obstructive syndrome in 36 children (main group) aged 2 to 14 years. Of these, with acute pneumonia - 16 children, with acute obstructive bronchitis - 20 children. The control group included 10 children who received traditional treatment (antibiotics, mucolytics, antipyretics, antihistamines).

Material and methods of research: All children were admitted to the hospital in the acute period, 2-3 days after the onset of the disease. Upon admission, all children of the main group were prescribed Inspiron for 7-10 days. The evaluation of the effectiveness of the drug was carried out on the basis of clinical symptoms - a decrease in the intensity of cough, as well as the rate of relief of broncho-obstructive syndrome throughout the entire period of the disease. The patients observed by us made 2 groups. Group I included 18 children aged 2 to 5 years. Group II included 18 children from 5 to 14 years old. Almost all patients had weakness, sweating, loss of appetite, headache, which accounted for 95%. In 85.3% of children, broncho-obstructive syndrome was accompanied by moderate to severe expiratory dyspnea, 72.3% of children had auscultatory dry rales on exhalation, 85% of children had an unproductive, not intense cough, 15% of children had a cough with difficult sputum separation. All patients underwent X-ray examination upon admission. Based on clinical data and X-ray examination, 55% of children from the first group and 25% of children from the second group were diagnosed with broncho-obstructive bronchitis; 33% of children from the first group and 56% of children from the second group were diagnosed with obstructive bronchitis with a

recurrent course. 12% of children from the first group and 19% of children from the second group were diagnosed with bronchial asthma.

In 75% of children with obstructive bronchitis and in 70% of children with obstructive bronchitis with recurrent course from the start of treatment on day 3, there was a significant decrease in the frequency of coughing. With a 7-day course of therapy, a positive effect was achieved, the disappearance of physical changes in the lungs in 90% of children with bronchial asthma and in 94% of children with obstructive bronchitis. Only in 10% of children, the continuation of the course of treatment required more than 10 days. None of the patients experienced side effects during treatment. Upon admission, the children were examined with a peak flow meter. Indicators of peak expiratory flow (PEF) were significantly lower than expected values and amounted to 50-60%. After treatment, PSV indicators in acute broncho-obstructive bronchitis with recurrent course and bronchial asthma were more than 80% of the proper values.

As a result of the use of the drug, a positive dynamics of clinical symptoms was observed on the third day. In 94.5% of cases, there was a decrease in the frequency of coughing and a decrease in its intensity, improvement in general condition, normalization of sleep and improvement in appetite. The severity of bronchial obstruction decreased on the third day by almost two times in contrast to the control group (1.2 times $p < 0.05$). On the fourth day from the start of treatment, distant wheezing was noted in 15% and 30% of children in the main and control groups of children, respectively. In 75% of children on the fifth day, the appearance of moist, well-separated sputum was noted. On the 5th day of treatment, broncho-obstructive syndrome stopped in almost all children (97.1% of the main group), and in those cases where manifestations still occurred, their severity was minimal.

Thus, the beginning of the use of the drug contributed to a more rapid disappearance of the clinical symptoms of respiratory infections and, accordingly, reduced the development of complications.

Conclusions: Given the safety of the drug inspiron, it can be used for coughing and broncho-obstructive syndrome in children. Inspiron is a safe starting anti-inflammatory drug in the treatment of bronchial obstructive syndrome in children against the background of viral and mixed etiology. The drug reduces the duration of coughing, accelerates the recovery time, eliminates the need for additional prescription of other drugs.

Thus, inspiron has a good anti-inflammatory effect in the treatment of acute and chronic inflammatory diseases of the upper and lower respiratory tract. It can be used as a complex anti-inflammatory agent in diseases of the upper respiratory tract to reduce the symptoms of inflammation. Since it has an antispasmodic effect on the smooth muscles of the bronchi and prevents the development of edema, it reduces the secretion of mucus from the nose and the amount of bronchial secretions. The drug can be widely used in chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases, bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis as part of complex therapy.

References:

1. Гелле Н.А. (2005) Применение эrespала (фенспирида) при ОРЗ у детей: эффективность и безопасность (результаты исследования по программе «Эльф»). Роль современной педиатрии, 4(2): 53-58.

2. Сорока Н.Д., Кобмунова Е.В., Гомозова С.П. и др. (2010) Опыт применения фенспирида в раннем реабилитационном периоде при пневмонии у детей. Пульмонология, 1: 93-98
3. Угли Ш. Н. М., Рустамов М. Р., Лим М. В. Е: I INDEX-Метод объективной оценки бронхообструктивного синдрома у детей //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 44-49.
4. Тоджиева Н., Курбаниязова В. Эффективность применения пролонгированного режима комбинированных оральных контрацептивов при лечении гиперпластических процессов эндометрия //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2016. – №. 4 (91). – С. 93-96.
5. Ризаев Ж. А. и др. Анализ активных механизмов модуляции кровотока микроциркуляторного русла у больных с пародонтитами на фоне ишемической болезни сердца, осложненной хронической сердечной недостаточностью //Вісник проблем біології і медицини. – 2019. – №. 4 (1). – С. 338-342.
6. Худоярова, Дилдора Рахимовна, and Гульноза Шавкатовна Шавкатова. "ЭНДОМЕТРИЙ ПОЛИПЛАРИНИ ТАШХИСЛАШ ВА ДАВОЛАШНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ ЖИХАТЛАРИ."
7. Худоярова Д., Абдуллаева Ш. ФЕТОПЛАЦЕНТАРНАЯ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТЬ И ГИПОТОНИЯ У БЕРЕМЕННЫХ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ ОБЗОР) //Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 1 Part 2. – С. 121-130.
8. Шавкатова, Гулноза Шавкатовна, Дилдора Рахимовна Худоярова, and Наргиза Нурмаматовна Абдуллаева. "МЕТАБОЛИЧЕСКИЙ СИНДРОМ И НОВЫЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ЕГО КОРРЕКЦИИ."
9. ISKANDAROVNA T. N., RAKHIMOVNA K. D. RISK FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENDOMETRIAL HYPERPLASTIC PROCESSES IN PREMENOPAUSE //БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ. – С. 72.
10. Khudoyarova D. S. D. R., Tilavova S. A., Shopulotova Z. A. MANIFESTATIONS OF EXAMINATION OF CHRONIC PYELONEPHRITIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN (CLINICAL CASE) //Thematics Journal of Microbiology. – 2022. – Т. 6. – №. 1.
11. KHUDOYAROVA D. R. et al. RESTORING NATURAL FERTILITY IN WOMEN WITH ENDOMETRIOSIS //БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ. – С. 43.
12. Tilavova Sitora Amirzoda, & Khudoyarova Dildora Rakhimovna. (2023). PHYSIOTHERAPEUTIC TREATMENT METHODS AND URINARY INCONTINENCE. International Journal of Medical Sciences And Clinical Research, 3(02), 05–12. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijmscr/Volume03Issue02-02>
13. Rakhimovna K. D., Abdumuminovna S. Z. THE ROLE OF STAPHYLOCOCCAL INFECTION IN THE STRUCTURE OF INFLAMMATORY DISEASES //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 1180-1183.
14. Sherbekovna, Eltazarova Gulnara, and Khudoyarova Dildora Rakhimovna. "ASSESSMENT OF THE SIGNIFICANCE OF POLYMORPHISM WNT3 GENE IN ANOMALIES OF FETUS DEVELOPMENT IN PREGNANT WOMEN OF THE SAMARKAND POPULATION." Art of Medicine. International Medical Scientific Journal 2.1 (2022).
15. Rizaev Z. A., Abdunosirovich R. R., Sharipovna N. N. Ways to improve the organization of dental services for chemical industry workers //The American journal of medical sciences and pharmaceutical research. – 2020. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 35-39.